

MOLYBDENUM CARBONITRIDE

By S. P. GHOSH

A ternary alloy containing molybdenum, nitrogen and carbon has been prepared and its structure has been elucidated by X-ray analysis.

Ternary metal—carbon—nitrogen systems have received very little attention. Deville (*Compt. rend.*, 1868, 66, 83) claimed to have prepared a niobium carbonitride of the formula $m\text{NbN}-n\text{NbC}$ by heating Nb_2O_5 with Na_2CO_3 in a graphite crucible at 1200° . Agte and Moers (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, 198, 233) have found by X-ray diffraction the existence of mixed crystals in the system $\text{TiC}-\text{TiN}$ and $\text{TaC}-\text{TaN}$. Stackelberg *et al.* (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1935, 175, 127) obtained a compound, $\text{Al}_3\text{C}_2\text{N}$ by the interaction of aluminium and carbon in presence of nitrogen at 1800° . Hausler (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, 154, 333) found that UC_2 could be completely converted into the nitride by heating in nitrogen at 1100° . No X-ray examination was made in this investigation. It is probable that an intermediate uranium carbonitride is formed. It has been shown by Riley (*Quart. Rev.*, 1949, III, 169) that there is a close crystallographic similarity between carbon and nitrogen and there should be a large number of intermediate phases containing both carbon and nitrogen in different alloy systems.

These intermediate phases could be prepared either by carbiding a nitride or nitrifying a carbide. There is no mention of molybdenum carbonitride in the literature. In the present work an investigation on the formation of molybdenum carbonitride was made by carbiding molybdenum nitride.

EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus used was the same as used for the preparation of molybdenum nitride (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 484). The circulatory pump used was designed by J. Gibson and others (*J. Sci. Inst.*, 1946, 24, 137). The pump incorporates a metal bellow and is connected to a valve system. In order to remove any CO_2 formed during the reaction, the system was provided with two condensation bulbs which were kept immersed in liquid oxygen. An outlet was also provided in the condensation system for taking out samples of gas for analysis.

A known amount of the nitride was taken in a silica boat and kept in the cold part of the reaction tube. The whole system was then evacuated and the furnace heated to the desired temperature. Pure CO was then admitted to the system. The pressure inside the system was maintained at the atmospheric level. Any CO_2 remaining as impurity with the CO was condensed in the condensation bulb. Thus the whole system was filled with pure CO . The volume of the gas as shown in the gas burette was noted before starting the experiment. The boat was then placed in the proper place inside the furnace with the help of the solenoid. The volume of the gas was noted every 10 minutes and the reaction continued till the disappearance of CO was negligible.

The volume of the gas consumed could not be determined accurately from the burette readings because of many variables; but it provided a rough idea of the gas intake. In the process of carburizing a nitride it is probable that the nitrogen atoms expelled may escape as cyanogen or nitrogen. After every run the CO_2 bulbs were heated up and the expelled gas was absorbed in caustic alkali. These solutions were found to contain cyanogen and in some cases paracyanogen.

The mixed nitride (β and δ), containing 42.2 atomic% nitrogen, was first carburized between 450° and 730° with carbon monoxide. The following observation was made:

- 450° ... Reduction to metallic molybdenum, formation of oxides and a trace deposition of carbon.
- 500° ... Complete conversion into MoO_3 .
- 600°-730° ... No reaction.

Higher temperature was not tried as the nitride was unstable.

The γ -nitride with a nitrogen content of 32.2 atomic% nitrogen was then carburized at 450° . The result was oxide formation. There was no detectable reaction at 600° . At 700° , CO reacts with the nitride with the formation of a ternary Mo-C-N phase. In the X-ray photograph of the product the lines of the face-centered cubic nitride were shifted toward the centre (Fig. 1) due to an expansion of the lattice.

FIG. 1

Molybdenum carbonitride

Molybdenum nitride (γ)

It was found that with longer hours of carburizing, as more carbon atoms went in replacing the nitrogen atoms, the lattice expanded more and more. But whilst there was a shifting of the lines of the γ -phase nitride, a new hexagonal phase also appeared. With higher carbon content this phase became more pronounced.

Table I shows the results of line measurement of a carburized nitride. The nitride originally contained 32.2 atomic% nitrogen. After 2 hours' carburizing the nitrogen content was found to be 26.9 atomic% and the carbon content was found to be 6.7 atomic%.

TABLE I

Intensity.	$\sin^2\theta$ (obs.).	h k l.	$\sin^2\theta$ (calc.).
m	0.9159	420	0.9184
m	0.8712	331	0.8724
vw	0.7358	400	0.7347
w	0.5516	222	0.5510
ms	0.5059	311	0.5051
ms	0.3697	220	0.3673
s	0.1858	200	0.1836
s	0.1401	111	0.1377

The lines were indexed as face-centered cubic. The value of a parameter was found to be 4.168 Å. The original nitride had an a value = 4.144 Å. So the increase in a value was 0.6%. The lines were, however, quite diffuse.

The same nitride was carbided for six hours; the product obtained contained 21.8 atomic% nitrogen and 15.7 atomic % carbon. Results of line measurements of a powder photograph are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Intensity.	$\sin^2\theta$ (obs.).	F. C. cubic		Hexagonal.	
		h k l.	Calc. $\sin^2\theta$.	h k l.	$\sin^2\theta$ (calc.).
m	0.9159	420	0.9172	003	0.9180
m	0.8706	331	0.8713	...	...
w	0.7885	...	...	112	0.7905
w	0.7332	400	0.7337	...	...
vw	0.6135	...	...	201	0.6120
w	0.5507	222	0.5503	...	...
w	0.5342	...	...	102	0.5355
s	0.5053	311	0.5044	...	...
m	0.4843	...	...	111	0.4855
w	0.3836	...	...	110	0.3825
s	0.3675	220	0.3668	...	...
s	0.2315	...	...	101	0.2295
s	0.1803	200	0.1834	...	...
vw	0.1533	...	...	...	...
s	0.1390	111	0.1375	...	...
ms	0.1285	...	...	100	0.1275
m	0.1029	...	...	001	0.1020

It is found that one set of lines belongs to the cubic γ -phase. The value of a parameter = 4.183 Å; increase in a is about 1%.

The other set of lines can be indexed as hexagonal of which the quadratic form is given by

$$\sin^2\theta = 0.1275 (h^2 + hk + k^2) + 0.1020 l^2$$

$$a = 2.888 \text{ Å}, c = 2.800 \text{ Å} \text{ and } c/a = 0.969.$$

The hexagonal phase became more pronounced when the carbiding was done at 800°. But the carbonitride phase was also found to be present.

The γ -nitride was then carbided at 850°. At this temperature the hexagonal phase was produced to a large extent as only some low angle lines of the γ -phase, which appeared as strong lines in the nitride, appeared as only very weak lines. Results of line measurements are given in Table III.

TABLE III

Intensity.	$\sin^2\theta$	Hexagonal.		F. C. Cubic.		Intensity.	$\sin^2\theta$	Hexagonal		F. C. Cubic.	
	(obs.)	$\sin^2\theta$	hkl.	$\sin^2\theta$	hkl.		(obs.)	$\sin^2\theta$	hkl.	$\sin^2\theta$	hkl.
		(calc.)		(calc.)			(calc.)		(calc.)		
m	0.9236					vw	0.5026	...	...		
m	0.9110	0.9090	003			s	0.4845	0.4850	111		
m	0.8889	...	...	0.8925	351	vw	0.4561	...	...		
m	0.8770	...	...			vw	0.4423	...	...		
vw	0.8633	...	...			w	0.4061	0.4040	002		
vw	0.8285	...	...			ms	0.3841	0.3840	110		
w	0.8003	...	...			vw	0.3730	...	...	0.3557	220
s	0.7875	0.7880	112			vw	0.3591	...	...		
vw	0.7306	...	...			vw	0.2948	...	...		
vw	0.6457	...	...			vw	0.2634	...	...		
s	0.6113	0.6130	201			vs	0.2307	0.2290	101		
vw	0.5555	...	...			m	0.1867	...	...	0.1878	200
s	0.5344	0.5320	102			vs	0.1294	0.1280	100		
s	0.5188	...	...	0.5167	311	ms	0.1028	0.1010	001		

There were quite a large number of weak and very weak lines which could not be indexed. A set of lines was indexed as satisfying the quadratic form:

$$\sin^2\theta = 0.1280(h^2 + hk + k^2) + 0.1010l^2$$

$$a = 2.883\text{\AA}, c = 2.830\text{\AA} \text{ and } c/a = 0.981.$$

Thus, with the introduction of more carbon the c parameter has increased from 2.800\AA to 2.830\AA. The a parameter has slightly decreased.

The low angle lines of the γ -nitride phase were also present, but only as weak lines. A rough value of a parameter calculated from these was found to be 4.121\AA. This value is much less than that of the γ -nitride (4.144\AA). Probably this phase is the original nitride phase, the lower a value is due to lower nitrogen content.

From these experiments it is concluded that no ternary Mo—C—N phase can be produced from the ($\beta + \delta$) mixed nitride. The γ -nitride forms an interstitial solid solution with carbon. This is supported by the expansion of the γ -nitride lattice on the replacement of nitrogen atoms by carbon atoms. The replacement is, however, not systematic as more carbon atoms get into the lattice than the nitrogen atoms expelled.

It could not be decided whether the hexagonal phase produced in the carbiding of the nitride is an interstitial carbonitride phase. According to Tamman (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, 124, 25) the β -molybdenum carbide has a hexagonal lattice with $c/a = 1.579$,

the carbon content being 5.08%. But in the case of the carbided product at 850°, the carbon content was 5.38% and the axial ratio, $c/a=0.981$. Thus, it appears that it might be possible to produce a simple hexagonal carbide by carbiding the nitride in contrast to MoC_2 , which has a close packed hexagonal lattice.

During the process of carbiding of the nitride the reaction, $2\text{CO} \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{C}_{\text{atomic}}$ occurred. There was very little tendency for the formation of graphitic carbon both in the case of the mixed ($\beta+\delta$) and the γ -nitride. The same observation has been made by Jack (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1948, **A**, 195, 41) in the case of iron nitride. This result supports the view expressed by Riley (*loc. cit.*) that carbon formation is not a surface phenomenon but occurs within the lattice.

The author expresses his best thanks to Prof. H. L. Riley for encouragement and discussion.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
KING'S COLLEGE,
NEWCASTLE-UPON-TYNE, ENGLAND
AND
SCIENCE COLLEGE, PATNA, INDIA.

Received August 19, 1952.